

Annex I

A schematic of the counter-current flow mode in the DCMD process is presented in **Figure S1**. The hot feed stream flows over a hydrophobic macroporous membrane while cold distillate flows on the other side of the membrane. The temperature difference between the membrane surfaces creates a difference of vapour pressure that drives the simultaneous transfer of mass and heat through the membrane by the evaporation of volatile components at the feed side, the diffusion of vapour molecules through the membrane pores and the vapour condensation at the distillate side.

Figure S1. Schematic representation of heat and mass transfer in counter-current flow DCMD configuration.

The distillate mass flux through the membrane can be expressed as [1]:

$$J_v = B_m \cdot \Delta p_m = B_m \cdot (p_{w,f}^0 - p_{w,d}^0) \quad (\text{S1})$$

where B_m [$\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{Pa}^{-1}$] is the overall membrane mass transfer coefficient, Δp_m [Pa] is the vapour pressure difference of vapour pressure of water in feed and distillate sides, $p_{w,f}^0$ and $p_{w,d}^0$ [Pa] are the water vapour pressures of feed and distillate sides at the membrane surfaces, respectively, and are calculated from the Antoine equation as:

$$p_{w,f}^0 = \exp\left(23.1964 - \frac{3816.44}{T_{f,m} - 46.13}\right) \quad (\text{S2a})$$

$$p_{w,d}^0 = \exp\left(23.1964 - \frac{3816.44}{T_{d,m} - 46.13}\right) \quad (\text{S2b})$$

with $T_{f,m}$ and $T_{d,m}$ [K] being the temperatures of the feed and the distillate solutions at the interface with the membrane, respectively. Considering the effect of salinity in the feed solution, Eq. (S1) becomes:

$$J_v = B_m \cdot (p_{w,f}^0 \cdot \gamma_{w,f} \cdot x_{w,f} - p_{w,d}^0) \quad (\text{S3})$$

where $\gamma_{w,f}$ [-] is the activity coefficient and $x_{w,f}$ [-] is the mole fraction of water in the feed. For an aqueous solution of NaCl, the activity coefficient is given by [2,3]:

$$\gamma_{w,f} = 1 - (0.5 \cdot x_{NaCl}) - (10 \cdot x_{NaCl}^2) \quad (\text{S4})$$

where x_{NaCl} [-] is the mole fraction of NaCl in the solution.

Referring to DCMD configuration in **Figure S1**, in the feed side fluid is at high temperature flowing over the membrane surface. Due to heat transfer resistance, the temperature at the membrane surface differs from the temperature in the bulk feed ($T_{f,b}$) or distillate ($T_{d,b}$). The temperatures at the membrane surfaces on the feed and distillate sides are calculated as [3,4]:

$$T_{f,m} = \frac{k_m \cdot \left(T_{d,b} + \frac{h_f}{h_d} T_{f,b}\right) + \delta \cdot (h_f \cdot T_{f,b} - J_v \cdot \Delta H_v)}{k_m + h_f \cdot \left(\delta + \frac{k_m}{h_d}\right)} \quad (\text{S5a})$$

$$T_{d,m} = \frac{k_m \cdot \left(T_{f,b} + \frac{h_d}{h_f} T_{d,b}\right) + \delta \cdot (h_d \cdot T_{d,b} - J_v \cdot \Delta H_v)}{k_m + h_d \cdot \left(\delta + \frac{k_m}{h_f}\right)} \quad (\text{S5b})$$

where δ [m] is the membrane thickness, h_f and h_d [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$] are the convective heat transfer coefficient in the feed and in the distillate side, respectively, ΔH_v [J kg^{-1}] is the enthalpy of vaporization of water and k_m [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$] is the effective thermal conductivity of the membrane.

The thermal conductivity of the membrane matrix can be determined by using the Isostress series model through the following relation [5,6]:

$$k_m = \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{k_g} + \frac{1-\varepsilon}{k_m} \right)^{-1} \quad (\text{S6})$$

with ε [-] the membrane porosity, k_g and k_m can be calculated in range of 273–373 K by [7,8]:

$$k_{g,water} = 2.72 \cdot 10^{-3} + 5.71 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot T \quad (\text{S7a})$$

$$k_{g,air} = 2.72 \cdot 10^{-3} + 7.77 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot T \quad (\text{S7b})$$

$$k_{m,PP} = -0.248 \cdot 10^{-3} + 1.3 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T \quad (\text{S7c})$$

The enthalpy of vaporization of water is taken as [9]:

$$\Delta H_v = 1.7535 \cdot T_{f,m} + 2024.3 \quad (\text{S8})$$

For both feed and distillate solutions, the convective heat transfer coefficient is calculated as:

$$h_i = \frac{Nu \cdot k_i}{d_h} \quad (\text{S9})$$

where d_h [m] is the hydraulic diameter of the feed channel or membrane module, k_i [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$] is the average thermal conductivity of fluid in the feed or distillate sides and Nu is the dimensionless Nusselt number. In case of laminar flow ($Re < 2300$), the following correlation for Nusselt number is valid [10,11]:

$$Nu = 1.86 \cdot \left(\frac{Re \cdot Pr \cdot d_h}{L} \right)^{0.33} \quad (\text{S10})$$

where L [m] is the characteristic linear dimension of the liquid path flow (corresponding to the longitudinal length of the active membrane module), Re is the Reynolds number and Pr is Prandtl number which is the ratio of viscous diffusion rate to thermal diffusion rate and is defined as:

$$Pr = \frac{\mu \cdot C_p}{k_i} \quad (\text{S11})$$

where μ [$\text{Kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$] is the dynamic viscosity and C_p [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$] is the specific heat capacity of the fluid. Re is the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces and is defined as:

$$Re = \frac{\rho_f \cdot v_f \cdot d_h}{\mu_f} \quad (\text{S12})$$

where ρ_f [kg m^{-3}] is the density of feed stream, v_f [m s^{-1}] is the flow velocity, μ_f [$\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$] is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid and d_h [m] is the hydraulic diameter of feed channel or module. For the membrane module shown in **Figure 2B**, d_h is calculated as $4 \cdot A/P$, where A [m^2] is the cross-sectional area within the membrane module and P [m] is the wetted perimeter (see module geometry in **Figure 2C**).

The values of the temperatures $T_{f,m}$ and $T_{d,m}$ calculated by Eqs. S5 can be inserted back in Eq. (S2) to determine the vapour pressures and then to calculate B_m from Eq. (S3).

The ratio of the temperature difference across the membrane to the bulk temperature difference is defined as the temperature polarization coefficient TPC [-], calculated as:

$$TPC = \frac{T_{f,m} - T_{d,m}}{T_{f,b} - T_{d,b}} \quad (\text{S13})$$

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